

Green Solutions for Overcoming the challenges associated with the green economy in Bangladesh

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Abstract

A green economy results in improved human well-being and social equity, while significantly reducing environmental risks and ecological scarcities. A green economy can provide growth-positive, employment-positive, and poverty-negative in Bangladesh. The study aims to identify the bottlenecks associated with the green economy in Bangladesh and find out green solutions. It was revealed that the 'grow first, clean up later' concept degrades the environment. Climate change and diminishing natural resources created an extra threat to sustainability. Toxic agriculture and the monoculture of rice impacted agrobiodiversity and generated many health hazards. Food adulteration has become a custom and tradition in the country, which is toxic, regardless of the method of intake. Some green solutions like green energy, green agriculture, green job, green transportation, green waste management, 3R, go green, biodiversity conservation, ecotourism, green investment and food security are recommended to overcome the challenges.

Keywords: Green economy, go green, greenwashing, 3R, green energy, green investment, ecotourism

Introduction

Over the decades, the notion of a green economy has become increasingly attractive to policymakers, academia and researchers. A green economy results in improved human well-being and social equity, while significantly reducing environmental risks and ecological scarcities (Victor & Jackson 2012; Musvoto *et al.* 2015; ten Brink *et al.* 2012; Kasztelan 2017). In its simplest expression, a green economy can be thought of as one which is a low carbon, resource efficient and socially inclusive (Georgeson & Poessinouw 2017; Borel-Saladin & Turok 2013). A green economy focuses on economic growth and employment reducing carbon emissions and pollution, accelerating sustainable development with minimum utilisation of natural resources and conserving ecosystem services (Wanner 2015; Ali *et al.* 2021; Kumar *et al.* 2021; Kasztelan 2017). Ecosystems or biodiversity finance and natural capital are the two major components of a green economy (Barbier 2011; Fletcher *et al.* 2019; Bobylev *et al.* 2015). It directly evaluates ecological services and treats natural resources as natural capital (Pearce *et al.* 2013; Loiseau *et al.* 2016). It is a component of the ecosystem in which it resides (Rosenbaum 2017; Pearce *et al.* 2013). The Economics of Ecosystem and Biodiversity study is important to implement the “Convention on Biodiversity”, which draws attention to the benefits of biodiversity and the costs of biodiversity loss and ecosystem degradation (Ring *et al.* 2010; Ten Brink 2011; Kumar 2012).

The economy for green is currently becoming a "buzzword" in Bangladesh (Ali 2018). Bangladesh is encountering severe environmental degradation, which hampers the economy. Economic activities also affect biodiversity and ecosystems. On the other hand, the resources are limited in the vast populated country. Resultantly, Green Economy is important in Bangladesh as it can reduce environmental risks and ecological scarcities; balance supply and demand; control carbon emissions; and increase resource efficiencies and social inclusiveness (Voumik & Shah 2014). A green economy can provide growth-positive, employment-positive, and poverty-negative in Bangladesh (Ahmed *et al.* 2012). There are many potential sectors such as renewable energy, buildings and construction, transportation, basic industries, agriculture and forestry etc. are the priority areas for the future green job market in Bangladesh (Bahauddin & Iftakhar 2013). On the other hand, it was reported that environmental degradation and depletion of natural resources in Bangladesh occur faster than in the past decades due to poverty and pressures of

overpopulation (Rahman 2023 a, b, c, d). Greenwashing occurs in food, beverage, cosmetics, medicine, brickfield, tourism and transportation sectors very often in the name of green (Rahman 2023e). Therefore, the study aims to identify the bottlenecks associated with the green economy in Bangladesh.

Methodology

Empirical data was used for this study. Three focus group discussions were carried out incorporating the respondents from diverse stakeholders like economists, environmentalists, local governments, community leaders, foresters, agriculturists, community leaders and industrialists. A total number of 10 key respondents were interviewed to find out the green solutions. Content analysis was done to interpret the data.

Challenges of the green economy in Bangladesh

“Grow first, clean up later”

The respondents opined that like other developing nations, Bangladesh follows 'grow fast, clean later' concept for economic growth. Incremental growth of urbanization and industrialization increase environmental degradation. The river and marine ecosystems face an onslaught threat because of the increased level of waste discharges and overexploitation of resources. Bhuyan & Islam (2017) reported that the marine biota is highly affected by pollution. It was argued that there is no exact information about the extent and gravity of the environmental degradation of the water resources in Bangladesh. Pollutions affect almost all people but the poor and the vulnerable are the worst affected. There is a positive correlation between water pollution and the incidence of water-borne diseases (Hasan & Jim 2019; Henry & Rahim 1990; Shaheen 2001). The capital Dhaka city is one of the worst polluted cities in the world (Ahmed *et al.* 2023; Mou *et al.* 2023). The respondents argued that air pollution in Dhaka city mainly occurs from industrial and traffic emissions. For years, air pollution has taken its toll on Bangladesh by harming lives and creating economic losses as well as environmental risks. Old vehicles, brickfields, dust from roads and construction sites, smoke from traffic jams and toxic fumes from industrial areas are major air pollutants in Bangladesh.

Environmental degradation and biodiversity loss

The respondents noted that gradual environmental degradation, climate change and diminishing natural resources created an extra threat to sustainability. A rapidly growing population are directly dependent on limited natural resources. Consequently, environmental degradation and depletion of natural resources occur at a faster rate. It has been accelerated by deforestation, habitat destruction and biodiversity loss. Due to overpopulation and limited land, the forest resources are overexploited.

According to respondents' perceptions, the consequences of habitat destruction are deforestation, decreasing vegetation coverage, soil degradation, loss of species richness, increasing rarity, loss of genetic diversity, loss of evolutionary potential, changes in water cycles and water tables, conversion of mixed stands into pure stands, destruction of natural regeneration, climate change, loss of ecosystem services, disruption of livelihoods of indigenous people, social instabilities, economic losses, loss of forest productivity, decreasing forest non-wood products; and increasing of environmental refugees.

The gradually increasing anthropogenic disturbances in the natural forests have made the system inhospitable for natural regeneration causing a net loss of biodiversity. It's an irony of fate that all our natural forests have become critically fragmented to the point where they are considered unlikely to maintain a minimum level of green coverage (Rahman *et al.* 2009; Rahman & Vacik 2009; Rahman 2021; Rahman 2022 a, b; Rahman 2023 f, k). The cities have become urban mayhem by losing living ambience (Rahman 2023 g, h).

Toxic agriculture and mono-culture of rice

The respondents highlighted that agricultural production in Bangladesh has increased tremendously over the last few decades through exploiting high-yielding varieties, chemical fertilizers and pesticides. Abuses of chemical fertilizers and pesticides have led to contamination of water, loss of diversity and deterioration of soil quality (Singh *et al.* 2018, 2020; Bisht & Chauhan 2020; Arora *et al.* 2018; Tripathi *et al.* 2020) Various health problems are associated with covert consumption of agrochemicals including pesticides. Agrochemical-based conventional agriculture also caused increasing vulnerability of crops to insect and pest attacks,

loss of aquatic life, declining yields, and deterioration of animal and human health (Rasul & Thapa 2003; Horrigan *et al.* 2002; Ehrlich *et al.* 1993). The respondents added that rice monoculture affects the associated biodiversity. Continuous application of urea and other pesticides for rice monoculture has negative impacts on water quality, wildlife populations, and human health (Rahman 2023i).

Food adulteration

The respondents opined that food adulteration has become a custom and tradition in Bangladesh. chemicals like calcium carbide are widely used for ripening fruit. The formalin is frequently used in perishable food items like fish, dressed chicken, fruits, vegetables etc. to keep them looking fresh to the buyers. Carbide reacts with water and produces acetylene gas, which is similar to ethylene, the fruit's natural ripening agent. Calcium carbide-treated fruits are acutely hazardous causing many diseases (Hossain *et al.* 2008; Hossain *et al.* 2015; Khan 2013). Formaldehyde is toxic to all animals, regardless of the method of intake (Islam *et al.* 2015; Wahed *et al.* 2016; Rahman *et al.* 2012). Pure, safe and organic food is a prerequisite for growing a green baby (Rahman 2023j).

Waste management

The respondents opined that waste management is a severe environmental problem in Bangladesh. The waste is generated from different sources like domestic, commercial, industrial, street sweeping, health services etc. They added that the concept of transfer stations, resource recovery, minimization and recycling are absent in our waste management system. The authorities are now grappling with the problems of high-volume waste, the costs involved, the disposal technologies, and the impact of waste on the environment.

Green solutions

The existing economy creates economic disparity, poverty, and environmental degradation. A green economy can serve all living organisms and offer antidotes to the current breakdown. The respondents suggested the following solutions overcome today's environmental mess.

Green energy: The rejuvenation green economy should focus on the energy sector. Bangladesh is in one of the most advantageous positions to generate sufficient renewable energy. The country

has abundant sunlight year-round, which is a rich source of renewable energy. It has hundreds of miles-long coastal areas, river banks, hilly areas, and islands providing plenty of wind for wind turbines.

Green job: This green energy revolution will create large-scale employment opportunities. A green job is related to preserving or restoring or maintaining the environment, producing energy from renewable sources, improving energy efficiency, preventing and cleaning up pollution and greenhouse gases, reducing carbon emissions and conserving natural resources.

Reduce, reuse, rethink: Living lightly on this God's planet, saving resources for the next generation and sharing resources with others should be the principle of the green economy. We should reduce our over-consumption, reuse our natural resources, rethink our over-consumptive lifestyles, and turn to the principles of simplicity.

Go green: From home to garden, food, health, technology, policy, politics, administration, economy, tourism, industrialization, urbanization and transportation there are millions of ways we can make our lives greener, and guide ourselves to go green. When we do something, those activities must benefit the green and our economy so that every single step of an individual helps to solve our social and environmental problems.

Green investment: We shall be happy to see small business grants and loans made to green companies so that they can survive, thrive and go for greener. It will be an immense pleasure to see the investments for all businesses going green and creating green job opportunities.

Green waste management: Green waste management puts the four R's-reduce, reuse, recycle and recover the resource into action.

Green agriculture: Green agriculture is the use of on-farm resources including crop residues, organic fertilizers, cropping diversification, mixed cropping, crop rotation and no use of chemicals for the maintenance and enhancement of biodiversity to make the agricultural system environmentally sustainable.

Green transportation: Green transportation is any sort of transportation or vehicle which has no negative impact on the environment. Walking, bicycling, electric scooters and bikes, green

vehicles (powered by solar, electricity, hydrogen, wind, or bio-fuels), car sharing, and public transport (buses, trains, and subway) are considered green transportation.

Pure food security: The goal of pure food security is to ensure that the public food supply is safe from disease caused by infection from human handling or by contamination from chemicals or other hazardous substances. Such contamination can occur during all phases of food production, including cultivation, harvesting, processing, packaging, storage, and cooking.

Biodiversity conservation: The main threats to our biodiversity are: habitat loss, habitat fragmentation, habitat degradation, colonization of alien species, overexploitation of natural resources, poaching, piracy, urbanization, industrialization, shifting cultivation, overpopulation, dependency on natural resources and climate change. Adaptive Collaborative Management, Integrated Conservation and Community based co-management can improve the current scenario.

Ecotourism: The universal definition of ecotourism is "responsible travel to natural areas that conserves the environment and improves the well-being of local people." The nexus of conservation, local people, and sustainable travel is ecotourism. The main principles of ecotourism are minimum impact, environmental and cultural awareness and respect, and direct financial benefits for conservation and local people.

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